

COMPARISON OF CSF ASPIRATION AND CONVENTIONAL POPPING METHODS USING 25-GAUGE SPINAL NEEDLE IN PATIENTS UNDERGOING SPINAL ANESTHESIA

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DOI: <https://doi.org/>

Article History

Received on 16 February 2026

Accepted on 20 March 2026

Published on 22 May 2026

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Abstract

Background: Performing spinal anesthesia with a thin gauge needle is technically difficult due to the flexibility of the needle and minimal pop sensation. In this study, we implemented a newly introduced technique of spinal anesthesia, that is the cerebrospinal fluid aspiration method, and compared it with the conventional popping method while using a 25-gauge Quincke type spinal needle.

Objective: The study compared the total procedural time, success rate of the first attempt to perform dura puncture, number of attempts, and incidence of post-Dural puncture headache using either CSF aspiration method or the conventional popping method in patients undergoing spinal anesthesia.

Design: Prospective, randomized, single-blinded controlled trial.

Participants: 60 patients between 19 to 65 years of age, with American Society of Anesthesiologists physical status 1 or 2, undergoing surgeries below umbilical region under spinal anesthesia were enrolled in this study.

Method: The patients were randomly assigned to one of the two groups: 1) Patients receiving spinal anesthesia using the CSF aspiration method, in which the spinal needle is advanced with continuous aspiration. 2) The conventional popping method, in which a Dural pop or click is sensed by the anesthesiologist. The primary outcome measure was the total procedural time and success rate of the first attempt to perform Dural puncture. Number of attempts, time to complete motor block, withdrawal cases, and post-Dural puncture headache were also recorded.

Result: 60 patients were included in this study. In the aspiration group, the total procedure time was significantly shorter than in popping group [P=0.039]. Moreover, In the popping group, the number of attempts was significantly higher than in the aspiration group [P = 0.018], whereas the success rate of the first attempt for Dural puncture was 93.3% compared to 70% in the popping group [P=0.020]. In the popping group, 4 withdrawal cases were reported, compared to aspiration group which had only one withdrawal case. There was no significant difference

between the number of passages and PDPH incidence between the two groups. However, 2 out of 60 cases of PDPH were reported, both belonging to the popping group.

Conclusion: The CSF aspiration method has several clinical benefits over conventional popping method for spinal anesthesia using 25-gauge Quincke-type spinal needle.

1. INTRODUCTION:

Spinal Anesthesia is an alternative form of general anesthesia, intended for incomplete neuromuscular blockade together with intra and post-operative pain management. The procedure involves injection of local anesthetic drug into the subarachnoid space, using a finely designed spinal needle. The desired effect is to block the transmission of afferent nerve signals from peripheral nociceptors, blocking the sensory signals and thereby eliminating pain.[1]

Spinal anesthesia is a technical procedure and requires skills to achieve the desired neuraxial block. And hence, there is a specific technique to accurately perform the puncture, referred to as 'conventional popping method' or 'loss of resistance' method.[2] Here, needle is advanced piercing the layers from skin till Dura matter, while the anesthesiologist senses 'click or pop' at 'ligamentum flavum' and then at 'Dura matter.' The stylet is then removed to observe free flowing CSF, followed with injection of the anesthetic drug.

However, technique-related adverse effects have been reported due to spinal anesthesia, such as backache, post-Dural puncture headache (PDPH), and transient neurological symptoms.[3] The appropriate external diameter of the spinal anesthesia needle is a key factor when opting for spinal anesthesia. With that being said, a variety of spinal needles have been introduced periodically.[4] These needles vary in diameter, length, orifice location and tip design, and are timely modified to simplify their use, depending on CSF outflow and ease of insertion.

Additionally, the orifice location and length of the needle is not much of a concern. However, the diameter of spinal needle plays a crucial role in success and outcomes of the spinal anesthesia.[5]

Thin gauge needles are proven to enable better flow of cerebrospinal fluid other than providing comfort of introducing local anesthetics.[6] Also, the smaller diameter needles show lesser incidence of PDPH and other mechanical complications compared to thick gauge needles. Fine gauge needles, i.e., 25-27 g are emerging as the choice of spinal pointers.

However, the conventional popping method of spinal anesthesia is considered technically difficult while using a less gauge needle. A thinner needle is more flexible, which restricts advancement of the needle in the intended direction. Additionally, the practitioner cannot feel the Dural puncture (known as the Dural click or popping sensation), which can lead to a higher failure rate when performing spinal anesthesia. [7]

Therefore, a new technique of spinal anesthesia has been introduced, specifically for small diameters, which is to advance the spinal needle in the subarachnoid space with 'continuous aspiration' into another syringe, applying negative pressure. This is called a 'CSF aspiration method.'

Hence, we hypothesized that the CSF aspiration method will provide more effective and safer spinal anesthesia, compared with the conventional method, when using thinner gauge needle.

The aim of this study was to compare the success rate, procedure time, number of attempts and PDPH complications between the aspiration method and the conventional popping method, using a 25G Quincke-type needle in adult patients undergoing spinal anesthesia.

Material And Methodology

It was a prospective comparative study, conducted over the course of six months, in the Department of Anesthesia and Critical Care, and Operation Theatre of Sindh Institute of Urology and Transplantation [SIUT].

A total of 60 patients, between 19 to 65 years of age, undergoing surgeries under spinal anesthesia, with American Society of Anesthesiologists physical status I and 2, and who fulfilled the study inclusion criteria were recruited. The patients were randomly assigned to one of two groups using a computer-generated random number table: patients in the popping group underwent spinal anesthesia using the conventional popping method; those in the aspiration group received spinal anesthesia using the novel aspiration method.

Inclusion Criteria:

Patients with informed consent present

Patients with hemodynamic stability

Patients with ASA grade 1 and 2

Patients between 19 to 65 years of age Patients with fresh laboratory reports (hematology and biochemistry) and fresh culture reports

Exclusion criteria:

Patients without informed consent

Patients with hemodynamic instability

Patients with ASA grade 3, 4 and 5

Patients below 19 years or above 65 years of age

Patients with any relative or absolute spinal anesthesia contraindications, i.e.

Raised ICP

Sepsis

Hypovolemia

Coagulopathy

Aortic or mitral stenosis

Neurological deficit

Localized or remote infection

Abnormal anatomy of vertebral column

On entering the operating room, the on-table examination was performed, with quick medical and nil per oral history, and pre-spinal vitals i.e., Heart Rate [HR], Non-invasive blood pressure, [NIBP], oxygen saturation [SPO₂], blood glucose levels, and temperature were recorded. All patients were coloaded with 5 ml/kg of crystalloids. Next, patients were placed in sitting position, with their legs flexed and back slightly bent forward with the support of a pillow, to bulge the spine for better palpation.

After disinfecting the patients' skin, the back was draped to ensure aseptic measures, followed with injection of local anesthetic (3 ml of lidocaine 2%) at the level of L3-L4.

Next, Spinal anesthesia was performed using a 25-gauge Quincke-type spinal needle at all times. The needle was introduced horizontally using midline approach in all patients.

In the popping method, the needle was advanced slowly, piercing the layers from skin till dura matter, while sensing a pop or click, indicating the Dural puncture. The stylet was then removed and the needle was observed for free flowing Cerebrospinal fluid, confirming the subarachnoid space. The needle was stabilized there using Bromage grip and the syringe containing local anesthetic was connected.

In the CSF aspiration method, cued by the sensation that the needle passed through the supra or intra-spinous ligaments, at the discretion of the operator, the stylet was removed and an empty 5 ml syringe was connected to the spinal needle and advanced while continuing aspiration with slight negative pressure till the cerebrospinal fluid (CSF) was detected in the syringe hub, confirming the subarachnoid space. The needle advancement was immediately discontinued then. The empty syringe was disconnected using Bromage grip and the one with local anesthetic was connected.

When performing the spinal anesthesia procedure by either of the two techniques, if the operator decided that the needle was too deep or was contacting the bone, the needle was withdrawn until the subcutaneous tissue while checked the flow of CSF without the stylet in the both groups.

Whereas, if CSF was present while withdrawing the needle, it was defined as a withdrawal case. This process of moving the spinal needle forward and backward movement was defined as a passage. If the operator could not confirm CSF flow during needle withdrawal, the needle was advanced repeatedly while changing its direction. If the operator could not confirm CSF flow during passages after 5 times, the attempt was regarded to be a failure. The needle was then completely removed and reinserted. If the operator could not confirm CSF flow even after 3 attempts, it was considered to be a failed case and the patient was excluded from the study.

After confirming subarachnoid space and CSF outflow, hyperbaric bupivacaine (12-15 mg of Sensocain 0.5% Spinal Heavy,) was injected according to the patient's height and surgical indication. The needle was then removed alongside the syringe. The patient was placed in supine position and sensory block was determined.

The variables were recorded by a second observer in both the groups, and included the pre- and post-spinal vitals, total procedure time, number of successful first attempts, total number of attempts, number of passages, withdrawal cases, post-spinal complications, i.e., post-Dural

puncture headache. Another significant variable included the “Bromage scale.” This was assessed after successful injection of local anesthetic drug and positioning of patient in supine position, to record the time used up to achieve the desired neuraxial blockade.

The primary outcome measure was the total procedure time, success or failure rate, total attempts and post-Dural puncture headache and were statistically analyzed. The enrolled patients were followed up until discharge to assess the occurrence of PDPH.

Total procedure time: Defined as time from spinal needle insertion to the injection of local anesthetic drug.

Post-Dural puncture headache: Headache that occurs within 5 days of lumbar puncture (LP), that is aggravated with standing or sitting position and relieved with lying down, and remits spontaneously within 2 weeks, or after sealing of the leak with epidural lumbar patch. [8]

Statistical Analysis

The sample size estimations were performed in accordance with data from the parent article, in which the success rate of first attempt was compared between the conventional popping method and aspiration method in 90 patients. We estimated that 60 subjects would be required to provide 95% power at a 5% significance level, which accounts for a 15% loss of study participants.

Statistical analyses were performed using SPSS 26. All data are expressed as mean (standard deviation), number (%), frequency or median as indicated. After testing for normally distributed data using the Kolmogorov-Smirnov test and Shapiro-Wilk test, continuous and categorical variables were analyzed using an independent sample t-test and a chi-squared test, respectively. Statistical significance was defined as $P < 0.05$.

Results:

Of the 60 patients enrolled in the present study, no patients were excluded from either group. Hence, each group comprised of randomly assigned sets of 30 patients.

There were no statistically significant differences in patient characteristics between the two groups. Patients were divided into two age groups: 1) 18-40 years of age 2) 41-65 years of age, whereas analysis showed majority of the participants of the total sample belonged to 41-65 years of age group (%). [Fig. 1.1]

Patients with American Society of Anesthesiologists physical status 1 and 2 were included in the study. On analysis, majority of the respondents were revealed to be ASA 2 (%) [Fig. 1.2]

Fig. 1.2. ASA grade analysis of total sample.

Data related to Dural puncture between the two groups are summarized in Table below.

VARIABLES	ASPIRATION GROUP	POPPING GROUP	STATISTICAL SIGNIFICANCE (P-VALUE)
Procedure time (30-90 secs)	22/30 [73.3%]	13/30 [42.14%]	0.039
Number of attempts (>1)	5/30	15/30	0.018
Success rate of first attempt	93.3%	70%	0.020
Withdrawal Cases	1/30	4/30	0.023

Fig. 2.1 illustrates the total procedure time between the two groups. In the aspiration group, the total procedure time was significantly shorter than in popping group [P=0.039], and majority of the cases, 22 out of 30, i.e., 73.3% achieved the

completion of spinal procedure in between 30-90 secs, compared to the popping group, which was 13 out of 30 cases, i.e., 42.14% of the total sample.

Fig 2.1. Comparison of total procedure time between aspiration and popping groups

In the popping group, the number of attempts was significantly higher than in the aspiration group [P= 0.018]. 15 out of 30 patients had more than one attempt in popping group, compared to 5 out of 30 in the aspiration group [Fig. 2.2].

Fig. 2.2 Number of attempts

In the aspiration group, the success rate of the first attempt for Dural puncture was 93.3% compared to 70% in the popping group [P=0.020] [Fig.2.3].

In the popping group, 4 withdrawal cases were reported, compared to aspiration group which had only one withdrawal case. Hence, there was significant difference in the withdrawal cases between both the groups [0.023]. [Fig. 2.4]

There was no statistically significant difference in the number of needle passages between the two groups [P=0.647].

The participants' length of hospital stay was between 2 and 5 days, and patients were followed until discharge for the occurrence of PDPH. Only two cases were reported out of 60 patients, belonging to popping group. However, no statistical significance was recognized [0.150].

Discussion

Spinal anesthesia is a technical procedure and requires skills to achieve the desired neuraxial block [9]. Though, it has enormous advantages in terms of patient's comfort, this type of regional anesthesia can result in noticeable complications, for example, post-Dural puncture headache, nerve damage or backpain, if not accurately performed.

To avoid post-spinal complications, certain measures are now considered, where the most important one is the needle diameter [10,11]. Studies show thin gauge needles are associated with lower incidence of post-Dural puncture headache, owing to their small diameters and consequently minute Dural punctures. Hence, fine gauge needles are now emerging as choice of spinal pointers.

However, performing spinal anesthesia using a 25G Quincke needle may be difficult, because of the low CSF pressure [9 to 28 cmH₂O], even in normal adults. Although a Dural click is observed, CSF flow may be insufficient in a spinal needle with a thin diameter of 25G in situations involving low pressure [12]. This increases the technical difficulties, thus resulting in prolonged procedure time, as well as repeated punctures. In this study, a shorter total procedure time as well as higher success rate was noted in the aspiration group. And so, the use of the aspiration method can help the operator detect the precise time of the Dural puncture [13,14].

Moreover, the number of attempts were also significantly lower in the aspiration group. These favorable results arise from decreased number of punctures, and lesser manipulation of the needle back and forth [15]. These outcomes suggest that the aspiration method can reduce complications arising from repeated advancement of the spinal needle [16]. Multiple attempts at puncture may result in direct damage to the spinal cord or nerves of the CNS [17]. Irritation of the filum terminale of the spinal cord causes paresthesia [18,19], and in severe cases, nerve damage [20,21]. There have been reports of damage to the conus medullaris [22] or discitis [23] after spinal anesthesia.

Also, aspiration group conveyed lower withdrawal cases, as the CSF is easily identified at the hub of the needle. Whereas, in the popping group the CSF flow was identified during backward movement of the needle. Here, we get the idea that this difference was because of the lack of click sensation in 25-gauge needle at the hands of an anesthesiologist, and the Dural puncture point was likely overpassed during insertion of the needle [24].

Furthermore, we opted for thin gauge needle to decrease the post-spinal complications, PDPH to be precise. However, post-spinal headache is not solely dependent on the needle diameter [25], and multiple attempts at puncture also adds to it [26]. In this study, two cases of PDPH were reported in the popping group, presumably because of additional attempts at Dural punctures [27, 28]. And, so we accomplish, the use of an aspiration method is appropriate when performing spinal anesthesia with a thin needle.

Considering the aforementioned challenges and outcomes, the result of this study concludes that the CSF aspiration method can be more effective and safer when than the conventional popping method.

Limitations

There were some limitations to this study. Firstly, the operator and the observer who recorded and analyzed the data were not blinded to the patients group. Secondly, as this study was conducted in urology centered hospital, majority of the participants were undergoing TURP procedures, with few exceptions of BSO, cystoscopy etc. Lastly, all patients were under 65 years of age and had no spinal deformity or history of previous spinal anesthesia. Thus, the results may not necessarily be applicable to different patient populations, particularly those of an older age or spinal diseases such as scoliosis.

Conclusion

The CSF aspiration method has several clinical benefits over conventional popping method for spinal anesthesia using 25-gauge Quincke-type spinal needle.

ABBREVIATIONS

PDPH: Post Dural Puncture Headache CSF: Cerebro-Spinal Fluid

TURP: Trans-Urethral Resection of Prostate BSO: Bilateral Salpingo Oophorectomy ICP: Intra Cranial Pressure

ASA: American Society of Anesthesiologists

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